

Influence Of Co^{2+} - Ni^{2+} Codopant On Mechanical Properties Of L-Asparagine Monohydrate Single Crystal

V. R. Sagane¹, G.G. Muley¹, Y.S.Tamgadge³ & P. M. Wankhade⁴

^{1&2}Department of Physics,

Sant Gadge Baba Amravati University, Amravati-444602, Maharashtra, India

³Department of Physics,

Mahatma Fule Arts, Commerce and Sitaramji Chaudhari Science Mahavidyalaya, Warud

Dist. Amravati

⁴Department of Physics,

Late R. B. Art's, Commerce & Smt. S. R. Bharti Science College Arni- 445103, Yavatmal

Maharashtra, India

Corresponding Author – V. R. Sagane

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.15260511

Abstract:

In the present investigation, single crystals of pure L-asparagine monohydrate (LAM) and Co^{2+} - Ni^{2+} doped LAM (CN-LAM) were grown by solution growth technique from aqueous solution at room temperature. Effect of dopant on mechanical parameters such as hardness number, yield strength and elastic stiffness constant have been carried out by indenting the load of 5, 10, 25, 50, and 100g on the surface of pure and Co^{2+} - Ni^{2+} doped LAM crystals with a fixed indentation time of 10s. Reverse size indentation effect has been confirmed by increasing nature of hardness graph with applied load. Value of hardness number and stiffness constant were found to be increase due to addition of co-dopant in pure LAM.

Keywords: Crystal growth, mechanical study.

Introduction:

Amino acid-based materials are among the most extensively studied organic materials for nonlinear optical applications. It contains donor carboxylic (-COOH) groups and proton acceptor amino acid (-NH₂) groups attached to the same carbon atom. Amino acid crystals display some interesting properties such as molecular chirality, absence of conjugate bonds, and zwitterionic nature. Therefore, grown crystals become noncentrosymmetric in nature; have higher transparency in visible region and harder in nature. L-asparagine monohydrate (LAM) is an amino acid that crystallized into orthorhombic crystal structure. The crystal structure reveals an intricate web of hydrogen bonds that bind

the L-asparagine molecule to water. In the literature, single crystal of LAM and metal doped LAM have been documented in the literature. Effect of dopant on various properties have been reported [1-9].

Numerous researchers have investigated the mechanical properties of various materials for device applications [10]. Vickers microhardness is recognized as a simple, effective, and precise method for determining a material's mechanical hardness. Key mechanical parameters include molecular binding, hardness value, stiffness constant, yield strength, brittleness index, fracture toughness, plasticity, and Knoop hardness number. For many optical device applications, materials with high hardness values are essential [11].

Consequently, efforts have been made to analyze the mechanical properties of pure and Co^{2+} - Ni^{2+} doped LAM crystals.

Experimental details and characterization:

The slow solvent evaporation method has been used to grow LAM and Co^{2+} - Ni^{2+} doped LAM crystals [6]. The crystal's mechanical strength was measured at room temperature using a Shimadzu-HMV-G tester. Prior to testing, the crystal was polished using polishing paper to get rid of any contaminants and flaws on its surface. By applying loads of 5, 10, 25, 50, and 100g to the crystal's surface [1 0 0] and maintaining a constant indentation time of 10s, the variation in microhardness number with applied load was examined. For every load, five indentations were created. To determine the exact value of mechanical parameters, the average of all diagonal lengths (d) for each crystal was computed.

Results and Discussion:

Effect of load on Vicker's microhardness and Meyer's index:

The hardness number was determined using the following equation: $H_v = 1.8544 \times P/d^2$, where d is the average diagonal length (mm), P is the applied load (g), and H_v represents the Vickers hardness number (kg/mm^2). Fig. 1 illustrates the hardness number as a function of the applied load. For both analyzed crystals, the increase in hardness with applied load confirms the RISE pattern [11]. The incorporation of Co-Ni dopants may lead to a more compact crystal lattice by reducing void spaces, thereby decreasing flexibility and enhancing resistance to deformation (hardness). Doped materials generally exhibit higher packing density, which correlates with greater mechanical strength [12]. Additionally, Meyer's index (n) for both crystals was found to be greater than 2, indicating that the grown crystals belong to the soft material category.

Fig.1. Load vs hardness number

Elastic stiffness constant(C_{11}) and Yield strength(σ_y):

The stiffness constant and yield strength were determined using formulas reported in the literature [13]. Figs 2 and 3 depict the variations of elastic stiffness constant and yield strength with the applied load, respectively.

The higher elastic stiffness constant observed in Co-Ni doped LAM crystals compared to pure LAM is primarily

attributed to the formation of stronger coordination bonds between the metal ions and the host crystal, leading to a more compact and rigid lattice structure. Additionally, factors such as electron density redistribution, enhanced cross-linking, and improved molecular interactions contribute to the increased stiffness constant, making the doped material more resistant to deformation under applied stress [12]. The

calculated mechanical parameters at a maximum load of 100 g are presented in Table 1.

Fig.2. Load P vs yield strength.

Table.1. Calculated mechanical parameter for pure and doped LAM crystals.

Sample Name	Hardness Number (Kg/mm ²)	Elastic Stiffness Constant (Pa) x10 ¹⁴	Meyers Index (n)
LAM	23.2	4.21469	3.33
Co-Ni doped LAM	24.7	4.70306	4.81

Fig.3. Load vs elastic stiffness constant.

Conclusions:

The Vickers microhardness study confirms the RISE effect in both pure and doped crystals, with the doped crystal exhibiting a higher hardness value than the pure crystal. The analyzed crystals fall into the soft material category. The incorporation of metal dopants enhances the stiffness constant, and Co-Ni doped LAM crystals demonstrate improved mechanical properties compared to pure LAM. Therefore, metal co-doped crystals may be suitable for device applications.

References:

1. A. Parvathi Priya, A. and Srinivasan, V.(2017). An Overview of Selective Amino acid Based NLO Crystals. *International Journal of Chem Tech Research*, 10(7), 12-17.
2. Suresh, T., Vetrivel, S., Gopinath, S., Vinoth. E. (2018). A new NLO Material: L-Asparagine thiocyanate (LATC) for opto-electronic applications *Chinese Journal of of Phycis*, 57,136-147. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cjph.2018.11.022>.

3. Jayaprakash, P. Sangeetha, P. Rathika Thaya Kumari, Baskaran, C. Lydia Caroline, I. M.(2017). Growth and characterization of L-asparagine monohydrate admixed dl-mandelic acid nonlinear optical single crystal, Journal Material Science: Material Electron, 28, 18787–18794. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10854-017-7828-z>.
4. Manikandan, S. Mahalakshmi, R. Krishnan, P. Yogam, F. Rajesh, P. (2016). Growth, structural, optical, thermal and dielectric properties of L-asparagine monohydrate admixed l-thiomalic acid single crystal. Optik 127, 5316–5321. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijleo.2016.03.036>.
5. Thukral, K. Vijayan, N. Haranath, D. Jayaramakrishnan, Philip, J. Sreekanth, P. Bhagavannaryana, G.(2015). Assessment on third order non linearity and other optical analyses of l-Asparagine Monohydrate single crystal: An efficient candidate for harmonic conversions, Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Mole. and Bio. Spectro, 151 419–425. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.saa.2015.05.051>.
6. Masilamani, S. Musthafa, A. M. (2013). Chemical analysis, FTIR and microhardness study to find out nonlinear optical property of L-asparagine lithium chloride: a semiorganic crystal Microchem. J. 110 (2013) 749–752. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.microc.2013.09.003>.
7. Suresh, T. Vetrivel, S. Gopinath, S. Vinoth, E. (2020). Investigation on synthesis, laser damage threshold, and NLO properties of L-asparagine thioacetamide single crystal for photonic device applications, Journal of Material Science, 31,13310–13320. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10854-020-03884-9>.
8. Gobinathana, L. Boopathy, K. (2015). Effect of potassium iodide on the growth and characterization of L-asparagine monohydrate single crystals, Der Pharma Chemical , 7, 362–367.
9. Meena, M. Sundararajan, R.S, Manikandan, E. Shalini, M. (2022). Diffractional, optical, electrical, NLO and surface studies of L-asparagine monohydrate lithium sulphate (LAMLS) single crystals, Journal of material science and Material Electron 33 (2022)18846–18857. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10854-022-08734-4>.
10. Dave, D. J. Parikh, K.D. Joshi, Vickers, M. J. (2017). Micro-hardness Studies of Amino acids (L-histidine,L-threonine and DL-methionine) doped KDP crystals, Advanced Material Research, 665,172178.doi:10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMR.665.172.
11. Suresh ,T. Vetrivel , S. Gopinath , Arul Joth, S. R. (2019). A new organic nonlinear optical material: L-asparagine cetrimonium bromide single crystal for photonic applications, Chemical Data Collection, 21, 100232. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cdc.2019.100232>.
12. Hameed, M. A. (2015). *Synthesis, Characterization, and Hardness Behavior of Co-Doped L-Asparagine Crystals*. Journal of Materials Science, 50, 4041–404.
13. Aneeba , B. Ashvin Santhia, S.V. Vinu , S. Alaa Baazeem , Sheela Christy , R.(2021). Effect of rare earth rubidium chloride on the optical, mechanical and antifungal behaviours of L-lysine monohydrochloride crystal for photonics and medical application, Journal of King Saud University Science, 33, 101443. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jksus.2021.101443>.